

BUCKLING BEHAVIOUR OF UD CARBON/EPOXY PANELS SUBJECTED TO DIRECT LIGHTNING STRIKE

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ABSTRACT

This research addresses the buckling response of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) panels damaged by simulated lightning strikes. The buckling response is evaluated through a combined experimental and computational investigation. Ten CFRP unidirectional (UD) eight ply laminate plate specimens were manufactured using a carbon/epoxy material system. The CFRP panel specimens were subjected to electrical current with a unipolar 10/350 μ s waveform simulating the first return stroke during a direct lightning strike in accordance with IEC 61400-24 Ed1.0 at 4 different lightning intensities (50, 75, 100 and 125kA). The buckling experiments were conducted in a newly designed modified buckling test, referred to as Compression After Lightning Strike (CALs), to accommodate for large composite panels and allow for the full lightning damage to be induced. The experimental results were benchmarked and compared against a 3D shell post-buckling finite element model (FEM). The FEM was run using the commercial finite element software Abaqus 6.14. The model was made up of shell elements, which represented the specimens and the damage induced by the lightning strike was taken into account by altering the material properties to have essentially no stiffness in the damaged regions. The results reported show good agreement between the experiment and the model predictions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Assessing the efficiency of lightning protection is an integral part of the testing/qualification of new wind turbine (WT) blade and aircraft designs. The introduction of conductive Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) composites has made lightning protection more challenging for these structures. CFRP materials, which are used due to their high specific stiffness and strength properties, are also effectively semi-conductors with strongly anisotropic electrical and thermal properties. Thus, CFRP materials exhibit properties different from conductive materials like e.g. metal alloys, making CFRPs more susceptible to lightning damage. The main reasons for this are the limited electrical and thermal conductivity transverse to the fibres. Lightning strikes can lead to damage in the CFRP especially due to elevated temperatures which cause loss of resin, fibre breakage, and delamination [1], [2]. In WT blades direct strikes occur when lightning attaches to the CFRP normal to the blade surface. This causes large current densities, which result in large temperature rises and damage in zones near the lightning attachment point. The effects of this have only been previously studied wrt. the inflicted material damage [3]. However, the effect of lightning strike damage on the structural response of CFRP WT blade structures has not been investigated previously. The compressive behaviour of CFRP sparcaps in WT blades is a crucial design driver, and the research presented here, for the first time, investigates the buckling response of a CFRP panel damaged by lightning.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 SPECIMEN MANUFACTURING

Ten CFRP unidirectional (UD) eight ply laminate specimens were manufactured using a carbon/epoxy material system. The carbon fibres are an 800 gsm fabric from Panex-35 by Zoltek and the epoxy system is Epilox ER5300 resin/EC5310 hardener. The eight laminates were manufactured

using vacuum liquid resin infusion. The laminates were manufactured to a dimension of 550 mm long x 500 mm wide x 7 mm thick. The plates were post cured at 70°C for 6 hours. The top edge was chamfered to an approximate 4:1 taper to expose the fibres for electrical grounding. An example of a laminate is shown in Fig. 1(a). Two of the samples were used as control specimens, and eight samples were subjected to direct lightning strike tests.

2.2 SIMULATED LIGHTNING STRIKE EXPERIMENTS

The CFRP panel specimens were subjected to electrical current with a unipolar 10/350 μ s waveform simulating the first return stroke during a direct strike according to IEC 61400-24 Ed1.0 [4]. The current was injected by a large current generator and an electrode with a gap of 20mm. The peak current subjected to the samples was 50, 75, 100, and 125 kA. Two of the damage samples are shown in Fig. 1(b) and 1(c). The lightning strike simulation setup is shown in Fig. 2(a).

Figure 1. Experimental specimens: (a) Control, (b) 50kA damaged and (c) 125kA damaged

Figure 2. Experimental setup for complete test: (a) lightning strike damage setup and circuit diagram; (b) structural test showing CALS rig

2.3 PLATE BUCKLING EXPERIMENTS AND FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A newly designed modified buckling rig has been manufactured with inspiration from the traditional ASTM compression after impact (CAI) test configuration [5], and the Sanchez redesigned CAI rig for thin laminates [6]. To capture the effects of lightning strike induced damage on the structural scale, the CAI rig was upscaled and redesigned. The new test configuration and rig is shown in Fig. 2(b), and is referred to as Compression After Lightning Strike (CALS). The upscaling was done to fit a variety of plate widths and lengths (larger than 500 mm), to closely resemble WT blade sparcap structures close to the blade tip where the propensity for direct lightning strike is the most severe. The rig was designed with interchangeable supports, and for the research reported a SSSS plate support system is used. The lightning strike damaged and control specimens were cut using a waterjet cutter to a final plate dimension of 500 mm square. The CFRP plates were loaded in the fibre direction

with a 0.5mm/min loading rate in compression. The tests were conducted to observe both the buckling and post-buckling responses until material failure was detected. Stereo 3D digital image correlation (DIC) is used on both side of the plate to capture the full field strains and displacements on both sides of the plate.

The experimental results were benchmarked and compared against a 3D shell post-buckling finite element model. The FEM was run in the commercial finite element software Abaqus 6.14. The model was constructed using shell elements that represented the laminate plate specimens. The damage induced by the lightning strike was taken into account by altering the material properties to have essentially no stiffness ($E=1\text{MPa}$). The extent (area and depth) of the damaged zones was estimated based on visual inspection and X-ray CT scanning of the damaged plate samples. An example of the FEM model used is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Example of finite element model and boundary conditions used for (a) undamaged and (b) damaged specimens

3 SAMPLE RESULTS

3.1 DIC RESULTS

The results from the DIC has shows significant differences between the control specimens and the damaged specimens. Figure 4 – Figure 6 shows the out-of-plane displacement for three different load levels. The results show that the out-of-plane displacements are much larger for the damaged sample specimen. The most severely damaged specimen (lightning strike of 125kA) for al load levels (Figs. 4-6), in addition to showing the highest displacement levels, displays a change in the displacement field, and further that the maximum displacement moves away from the damaged region. This indicates that the stiffness in the damaged regions was significantly reduced by the lightning strike events.

Figure 4. Full field experimental results of out-of-plane displacement from stereo DIC at 60 kN compressive load for the control specimen, and lightning damaged specimens struck with 50 kA and 125kA

Figure 5. Full field experimental results of out-of-plane displacement from stereo DIC at 120 kN compressive load for the control specimen, and lightning damaged specimens struck with 50 kA and 125kA

In Figure 6, discontinuities in the contour plots show regions of plies failing. This shows that the failure load is lower for the damaged samples than for the control.

Figure 6. Full field experimental results of out-of-plane displacement from stereo DIC at 180 kN compressive load for the control specimen, and lightning damaged specimens struck with 50 kA and 125kA

3.2 FEM RESULTS

The damage regions were modelled by assuming an elliptical shape with equal area to the damage seen on the surface. The number of plies to remove in the modelling was determined by X-ray CT scans. Considering the simplicity of this modelling approach, the predicted out-of-plane displacement field match well with the DIC results. Figure 7 – Figure 9 show the FEM results (compare against DIC results in Figs. 4-6). It is observed that the features from

the DIC results are represented in the FEM predictions as well including the change/shift in displacement patterns.

Figure 7. FEM predictions of out-of-plane displacement at 60 kN compressive load for the control specimen, and lightning damaged specimens struck with 50 kA and 125kA

Figure 8. FEM predictions of out-of-plane displacement at 120 kN compressive load for the control specimen, and lightning damaged specimens struck with 50 kA and 125kA

Figure 9. FEM results of out-of-plane displacement at 180 kN compressive load for the control specimen, and lightning damaged specimens struck with 50 kA and 125kA

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the buckling behaviour of CFRP plate panels representative for wind turbine blade sparcap laminates impacted with simulated lightning strikes. A specially adapted compression loading test, the Compression After Lightning Strike (CALs), was proposed and commissioned to include important structural scale effects not included in conventional Compression After Impact (CAI) coupon tests. The full field out-of-plane displacements were measured using DIC at different load levels for undamaged and lightning strike damages laminate specimens. The measured displacement fields were benchmarked against FEM predictions that include the damaged zones and a reasonable match was found

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